

HYDROXY- AND ALKOXY-ALKYLBIGUANIDE METAL COMPLEXES. PART IV. INSTABILITY CONSTANTS OF COPPER AND NICKEL COMPLEXES

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The instability constants of copper and nickel complexes of hydroxy- and alkoxy-alkylbiguanides have been determined spectrophotometrically from a study of their formation reaction in solution. The acid dissociation constants k_{a1} and k_{a2} of the ligands have been determined, following the method suggested by Bjerrum (cf. Das Sarma, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 217). It has been found that the basic character of the ligand increases with the introduction of a hydroxyl group in the alkyl radical of the substituted biguanide molecules. The stability constants of nickel complexes of hydroxy- and alkoxy-alkylbiguanides are also somewhat greater than those of their corresponding alkylbiguanides.

The present work was undertaken with a view to making a systematic and quantitative study of the influence of hydroxyl and alkoxy groups in a substituted biguanide molecule on the stability of their complexes with bivalent metals like copper and nickel, as also on the relative stability of the two metallic complexes.

The acid dissociation constants of ethanol-, propanol-, methoxyethyl- and methoxypropylbiguanides have been determined for this purpose, following the method suggested by Bjerrum ("Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941; cf. Das Sarma, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 217).

In acid solutions biguanide is present as biguanidinium ion. In low acid concentration it occurs mostly as $s\text{-BigH}_2^+$ ion, the concentration of $s\text{-BigH}_3^{2+}$ ion being negligible:

where $s\text{-BigH}$ = one molecule of hydroxy- or alkoxy-alkylbiguanide.

Therefore:

$$k_{a1} = \frac{[s\text{-BigH}][\text{H}^+]}{[s\text{-BigH}_2^+]}$$

and similarly

$$k_{a2} = \frac{[s\text{-BigH}_2^+][\text{H}^+]}{[s\text{-BigH}_3^{2+}]}$$

The square bracket indicates concentration. The experimental conditions were chosen to ensure a low concentration of the reactants in the presence of a large quantity of 0.2M-KCl for maintaining a constant ionic strength.

The values of k_{a1} and k_{a2} are obtained from the formation curves traced by plotting $\bar{\eta}$ against the pH values (Fig. 1), when $\bar{\eta} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively (*loc. cit.*).

The value of the first acid dissociation constant k_{a1} of these ligands can be arranged in the following order along with that of ethylbiguanide (cf. Das Sarma, *loc. cit.*) and propylbiguanide (Sengupta and Dutta, unpublished work), for comparison:

It shows that the basicity increases with the introduction of a hydroxyl group in the substituent. The alkoxy group in the substituent, on the other hand, exerts little effect on the basicity of the ligand as is evident from k_{a1} value of the methoxyethylbiguanide, which is practically the same as that of the ethylbiguanide.

FIG. 1

Curve "A"-Ethanolbiguanide. Curve "B"-Propanolbiguanide. Curve "C"-Methoxyethylbiguanide.
Curve "D"-Methoxypropylbiguanide.

Instability Constants.—The hydroxy- and alkoxy-alkylbiguanides give rise to water-soluble coloured complexes with copper and nickel ions (vide Part 1, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 373). The instability constants of the complexes have been determined from the measurement of optical density of their solutions.

(i). **System : Copper complexes.**—When a metal ion is mixed with hydroxy- or alkoxy-alkylbiguanide solution in the form of chloride (perchlorate or nitrate cannot be used as they form sparingly soluble precipitates) in the molar ratio of 1:3 in the presence of a neutral salt (to maintain

a constant ionic strength), the formation of a coloured complex occurs in solution at certain pH values. Up to pH 3, the bluish green colour of copper ion persists; this gradually changes to a blue colour (*mono-complex*) above pH 3, exhibiting absorption maxima at 650 to 670 $m\mu$, the colour intensity reaching a maximum at pH 4 to 5. Above pH 5, the solution develops a pink colour (*bis-complex*), having an absorption maximum at 520 to 540 $m\mu$ (Fig. 2; also cf. Ray and Rây, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 849).

FIG. 2

Absorption spectra of metal complexes.

Curve "A"—Ni-complex. Curve "B"—Cu-*bis*-complex. Curve "C"—Cu-*mono*-complex.

(ii). *System: Nickel complexes.*—Nickel develops an orange-yellow colour above pH 6.5, with the solution of an excess of a hydroxy- or alkoxy-alkylbiguanide. The colour shows an absorption maximum at 460–480 $m\mu$, characteristic of diamagnetic nickel biguanide complexes (Fig. 3.).

Molar Extinction Coefficient.—The molar extinction coefficients of the blue (*mono*) and pink (*bis*) copper complexes as well as of the nickel complex were evaluated from the optical density values (from the O.D./pH curve) measured at the wave-length of absorption maximum of the respective complexes (Figs. 3, 4 and 5). The molar extinction coefficients of copper *mono*-complexes at the wave-length corresponding to the absorption maximum of copper-*bis*-complexes were obtained from

the O.D. values at that wave-length of solutions at pH 4 to 5 in which the concentration of the *mono*-complex would become maximum.

FIG. 3

Formation of Cu-mono-complexes

Curve "a"-Ethanolbiguanide. Curve "b"-Propanolbiguanide. Curve "c"-Methoxyethylbiguanide.
Curve "d"-Methoxypropylbiguanide.

For the copper-ligand systems depending on the pH of the solutions, there may exist two distinct equilibria: (i) between the hydrated copper ion (bluish green) and the copper *mono*-complex (blue) and (ii) between the copper *mono*-complex (blue) and the copper *bis*-complex (pink). In the case of nickel, however, only one equilibrium, *i.e.*, between the hydrated nickel ion (green) and the nickel *bis*-complex (orange-yellow) has been found to occur.

FIG. 4

Formation of Cu-bis-biguanide complexes.

Curve "a"-Ethanolbiguanide. Curve "b"-Propanolbiguanide. Curve "c"-Methoxyethylbiguanide.
Curve "d"-Methoxypropylbiguanide.

The interference due to the chloro-complex of copper has been discussed critically by Ray and Rây (*loc. cit.*; 1959, 36, 858) and in the light of their discussion, the influence of any chloro-complex of copper may be ignored in the evaluation of the stability constants of copper *mono*-biguanide complexes.

The concentration of any coloured species (A or B) in a system in equilibrium can be calculated from the following equation (cf. Ray and Rây, *loc. cit.*):

$$C_A = \frac{D - \epsilon_B \cdot C}{\epsilon_A - \epsilon_B}; C = C_A + C_B$$

where ϵ and C signify respectively the molar extinction coefficient and concentration of the coloured species.

FIG. 5

Formation of Ni-bis-biguanide complexes.

Curve "a"-Ethanolbiguanide. Curve "b"-Propanolbiguanide. Curve "c"-Methoxyethylbiguanide.
Curve "d"-Methoxypropylbiguanide.

Instability Constants

(a). *Copper complexes.*—The biguanide salts and the copper ion in solution form complexes like $[\text{Cu}(\text{s-BigH})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{s-BigH})_2]^{2+}$ depending on the pH of the solution.

Hence the equilibrium constants kf'_1 and kf'_2 of the reactions (5) and (6) are given by :

$$kf'_1 = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{s-BigH})^{2+}] \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]} \quad \dots (7)$$

and

$$kf'_2 = \frac{[\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}] \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cu}^-(\text{s-BigH})_2^{2+}] \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]} \quad \dots (8)$$

Let $C_2 = [\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}]$, $C_1 = [\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}]$, $\alpha =$ initial metal-ion concentration and $\beta =$ initial biguanide concentration.

Therefore kf'_1 and kf'_2 are given by (cf. Ray and Rây, *loc. cit.*):

$$kf'_1 = \frac{C_1 \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_1) \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]} \quad \dots (9)$$

i.e.,

$$kf'_1 = \frac{C_1 \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_1) (\beta - C_1)} \left\{ 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_{a2}} \right\} \quad (10)$$

and

$$kf'_2 = \frac{C_2 \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_2) \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]} \quad \dots (11)$$

i.e.,

$$kf'_2 = \frac{C_2 \cdot [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_2) (\beta - \alpha - C_2)} \quad \dots (12)$$

Now the successive instability constants k_2 and k_1 are derived from:

and

i.e.,

$$k_2 = \frac{[\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}] \cdot [\text{s-BigH}]}{[\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}]} = \frac{1}{kf'_2} \times k_{a1}$$

and

$$k_1 = \frac{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] \cdot [\text{s-BigH}]}{[\text{Cu (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}]} = \frac{1}{kf'_1} \times k_{a1}$$

Therefore the overall instability constant (K) for copper complex = $k_1 \times k_2$

i.e.,

$$K = \frac{(k_{a1})^2}{kf'_1 \times kf'_2} \quad (13)$$

(b). *Nickel complexes.*—Nickel reacts with hydroxy- or alkoxy-alkylbiguanide in one step to form bis-hydroxy- or alkoxy-alkylbiguanide complex:

The equilibrium constant for the reaction is given by:

$$kf' = \frac{[\text{Ni (s-BigH)}_2^{2+}] \cdot [\text{H}^+]^2}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}] \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]^2} \quad \dots (14)$$

i.e.

$$kf' = \frac{C_0 \cdot [\text{H}^+]^2}{(\alpha - C_0) \cdot [\text{s-BigH}_2^+]^2} \quad (\text{vide copper})$$

$$= \frac{C_0 \cdot [H^+]^2}{(\alpha - C_0) \cdot (\beta - 2C_0)} \quad \dots (15)$$

where $C_0 = [Ni (s-BigH)_2^{2+}]$. Therefore the instability constant K of the nickel complex is derived from :

$$K = \frac{[Ni^{2+}] \cdot [s-BigH]^2}{[Ni (s-BigH)_2]} = \frac{1}{kf'} \times (k_{a_1})^2 \quad \dots (17)$$

The values of the instability constants of copper and nickel complexes are recorded in Tables I-V.

A comparative statement of the instability of the metal complexes of hydroxyalkyl, alkoxy-alkyl and some of the alkyl biguanides are recorded in Table VI. It may be concluded that the introduction of a hydroxyl and a methoxyl group in a substituent in the biguanide molecule increases the stability of the nickel complexes. The value of the instability constant of the copper ethanol-biguanide complex is somewhat approximate due to a slight hydrolytic reaction leading to the formation of a binuclear copper complex. The nickel complexes are less stable (about 10^{-4} times) than the corresponding copper complexes. Comparing the relative basic strengths of the hydroxy- and alkoxy-alkylbiguanides with the relative stabilities of their copper or nickel complexes, it may be concluded that there is no simple relation between the two. It should, however, be noted that while the formation of the copper complexes occurs through two successive steps, the nickel complexes are formed in a single step.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. Acid Dissociation Constants of Hydroxy- and Alkoxy-alkylbiguanides

A solution of hydroxyalkylbiguanide monohydrochloride (0.05M) or of alkoxyalkylbiguanide dihydrochloride (0.05M) was prepared from a solution of pure recrystallised hydroxyalkylbiguanide sulphate or alkoxyalkylbiguanide acid sulphate (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*) by treatment with a little excess of the requisite quantity of barium chloride solution, filtering from the precipitated barium sulphate, and diluting to a definite volume with water. An aliquot of the biguanide hydrochloride solution (0.05M, 10 c.c.) was taken in each of several 50 c.c. standard volumetric flasks along with 10 c.c. of KCl (1M) solution and to these different amounts of standard hydrochloric acid or caustic potash solutions were added as required and the resulting solutions were made up to 50 c.c. These were kept at $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ for a day, and next day the pH of the solutions was measured using a glass electrode (up to pH 8) or an alkylglass electrode (from pH 9 and above), against a saturated calomel reference electrode, in the Cambridge pH meter. The pH meter was set against a buffer solution of known pH. The values of k_{a_1} and k_{a_2} were obtained from the $\bar{\eta}$ values plotted against pH (Fig. 1).

	Ethanol biguanide	Propanol biguanide	Methoxyethyl biguanide	Methoxypropyl biguanide
$k_{a_1}(\bar{\eta}=0.5)$	2.98×10^{-12}	3.16×10^{-12}	3.38×10^{-12}	3.98×10^{-12}
$k_{a_2}(\bar{\eta}=1.5)$	1.58×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-3}	0.83×10^{-3}

B. *Instability Constants of Metal Complexes*

A solution of the metal ion (i.e. metal chloride) of known strength and that of the biguanide hydrochloride were mixed in the molar ratio (1:3 in the case of copper complexes and 1:3 to 1:6 in the case of nickel complexes) in a 50 c.c. volumetric flask. A large excess of the ligand in the case of nickel complexes was found to be necessary in order to prevent hydrolysis of the complex. The pH of the solutions was adjusted to different values by the addition of alkali. A definite amount (10 c.c. of 1M solution) of KCl solution was added to each flask before making up the volume. The pH and the absorption spectra of solutions were measured (in Unicam SP 600) after allowing the mixture to attain equilibrium at $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ for about 24 hours. The results are recorded in the tables.

TABLE I (cf. Fig. 3, curve b)

Formation of copper mono-propanolbiguanide complex.

$\alpha = 0.005047M.$		$\epsilon_{\text{Cu-mono-complex}} = 34.67$		$k_{a_1} = 3.16 \times 10^{-12}$		
$\beta = 0.015M.$		$\epsilon_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} = 5.00$		$k_{a_2} = 1.00 \times 10^{-3}$		
KCl = 0.2M.		Wave-length = 650 m μ .		Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$.		
pH.	O.D (1 cm).	C_1 .	$(\alpha - C_1)$.	$(\beta - C_1)$.	$[a - \text{BigH}_2^+]$	$kf'_1 \times 10^4$.
					$= \frac{(\beta - C_1)}{(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_{a_1}})}$	
3.5	0.061	0.001206	0.003841	0.013794	0.01048	0.95
3.6	0.070	0.001509	0.003538	0.013491	0.01078	0.99
3.7	0.080	0.001846	0.003201	0.013154	0.01096	1.05
3.8	0.090	0.002183	0.002864	0.012817	0.01106	1.09
3.9	0.102	0.002587	0.002460	0.012413	0.01103	1.20
4.0	0.112	0.002925	0.002122	0.012075	0.01102	1.25
4.1	0.122	0.003261	0.001786	0.011739	0.01088	1.33
4.2	0.133	0.003634	0.001413	0.011366	0.01070	1.52

$$kf'_1 \text{ (average)} = 0.0117$$

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{kf'_1} \times k_{a_1} = 2.7 \times 10^{-10}$$

TABLE II (cf. Fig. 4, curve b)

Formation of copper bis-propanolbiguanide complex.

$\alpha = 0.005047M.$		$\epsilon_{\text{Cu-bis-complex}} = 45.10.$		$k_{a_1} = 3.16 \times 10^{-12}$	
$\beta = 0.015M.$		$\epsilon_{\text{Cu-mono-complex}} = 9.32.$		$k_{a_2} = 1.00 \times 10^{-3}$	
KCl = 0.2M.		Wave-length = 530 m μ .		Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$.	
pH.	O.D (1 cm).	C_1 .	$(\alpha - C_1)$.	$(\beta - \alpha - C_2)$.	$kf'_2 \times 10^4$.
5.8	0.120	0.001699	0.003348	0.008254	9.81
5.9	0.125	0.001839	0.003208	0.008114	8.90
6.0	0.133	0.002062	0.002985	0.007891	8.75
6.1	0.142	0.002314	0.002733	0.007639	8.61
6.2	0.147	0.002453	0.002596	0.007498	7.95
6.3	0.155	0.002677	0.002370	0.007276	7.78
6.4 _a	0.163	0.002900	0.002147	0.007053	7.63
6.5	0.172	0.003152	0.001895	0.006801	7.73
6.6	0.180	0.003375	0.001672	0.006578	7.72
6.7	0.190	0.003655	0.001392	0.006298	8.32

$$kf'_2 \text{ (average)} = 8.24 \times 10^{-5}$$

$$k_2 = \frac{1}{kf'_2} \times k_{a_1} = 0.38 \times 10^{-7}$$

Therefore $K = k_1 \times k_2 = 1.03 \times 10^{-17}$.

TABLE III (cf. Figs. 3 and 4)

Copper complexes.

Complex	$\beta = 0.015M$.	KCl = 0.2M	Temp. = $30^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$.	$\epsilon_{Cu^{2+}} = 5.00$.				
	ϵ_1 (640 — 650m μ), ϵ_2 (520 — 540 m μ), ϵ_3 (520 — 540 m μ), $k_1' \times 10^3$.		$k_2 \times 10^7$.	$k_3 \times 10^7$.				
Cu-ethanolbiguanide complex (cf. curve a)	47.39	46.89	13.60	2.71	1.10	2.64	1.13	1.24
$\alpha = 0.005M$								
Cu-propanolbiguanide complex (cf. curve b)	34.67	45.10	9.32	1.17	2.07	8.24	0.38	1.03
$\alpha = 0.005M$								
Cu-methoxyethylbiguanide complex (cf. curve c)	43.35	47.39	9.48	1.99	1.70	10.39	0.32	0.56
$\alpha = 0.005M$								
Cu-methoxypropylbiguanide complex (cf. curve d)	37.80	47.80	10.78	1.32	3.02	10.25	0.39	1.17
$\alpha = 0.005M$								

ϵ_1 and ϵ_3 stand for the molar extinction coefficients of copper-mono-hydroxy and alkoxy-alkyl and copper-bis-hydroxy- and alkoxy-alkylbiguanide complexes respectively.

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 5, curve a)

Formation of nickel bis-ethanolbiguanide complex.

$\alpha = 0.002274M.$ $\beta = 0.02M.$ $KCl = 0.2M.$		$\epsilon_{Ni\text{-complex}} = 51.00.$ $\epsilon_{Ni^{2+}} = 1.00.$ Wave-length = 460 m μ .	$k_{a_1} = 2.98 \times 10^{-12}.$ $k_{a_2} = 1.58 \times 10^{-8}.$ Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 2^\circ.$		
pH.	O.D (1 cm).	$C_0.$	$(\alpha - C_0).$	$(\beta - 2C_0).$	$kf' \times 10^{11}.$
7.00	0.0490	0.0009326	0.0013414	0.0181348	2.11
7.10	0.0575	0.0011040	0.0011700	0.0177920	2.37
7.20	0.0660	0.0012750	0.0009990	0.0174500	2.64
7.30	0.0750	0.0014540	0.0008200	0.0170920	3.04
7.40	0.0850	0.0016550	0.0006190	0.0166900	3.82
7.50	0.0900	0.0017540	0.0005200	0.0164920	3.92

$$kf' \text{ (average)} = 2.98 \times 10^{-11}$$

$$K = \frac{1}{kf'} \times k_{a_1}^2 = 2.97 \times 10^{-13}$$

TABLE V (cf. Fig. 5)

Nickel complexes.

Complex.	$\beta = 0.015M.$ $KCl = 0.2M.$ $Temp. = 30^\circ \pm 2^\circ.$ $\epsilon_{Ni^{2+}} = 1.00.$	$\epsilon_{Ni\text{-complex}} (460-470 m\mu).$	$kf' \times 10^{11}.$	$K \times 10^{13}.$
Ni-propanolbiguanide complex (curve b) $\alpha = 0.005M$		48.71	2.10	4.76
Ni-methoxyethylbiguanide complex (curve c) $\alpha = 0.0025M$		66.69	1.05	10.94
Ni-methoxypropylbiguanide complex (curve d) $\alpha = 0.0024M$		64.21	0.89	17.72

TABLE VI

Ligand.	$k_1(Cu) \times 10^{19}.$	$k_2(Cu) \times 10^7.$	Instability constant (overall).	
			$K_{Cu} \times 10^{17}.$	$K_{Ni} \times 10^{13}.$
Ethanolbiguanide	.. 1.10	1.13	1.24	2.97
Propynolbiguanide	.. 2.70	0.38	1.03	4.76
Methoxyethylbiguanide	.. 1.70	0.32	0.56	10.94
Methoxypropylbiguanide	.. 3.02	0.39	1.17	17.72
*Biguanide	.. 0.80	0.06	0.05	0.33
*Methylbiguanide	.. 3.00	0.24	0.72	16.60
*Ethylbiguanide	.. 3.70	0.28	1.04	16.63

*Studied by Das Serma and Ray (this Journal, 1956, 33, 841)